

HARMFUL ALGAE NEWS

An IOC Newsletter on toxic algae and algal blooms

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No. 31

• France

Identification of *Pseudo-nitzschia australis* and *P. multiseriata* in the Bay of Seine. Was there a relation to presence of domoic acid in king scallops in autumn 2004?

In late 2004, the French phytoplankton monitoring network (REPHY of Ifremer) detected domoic acid (DA) above the EU-regulatory limit of 20 µg DA/g tissue in king scallops (*Pecten maximus*) from the Bay of Seine in the Channel (Fig. 1). Shellfish harvesting sites were closed for several months due to slow depuration of the scallops.

Accumulation of DA in French shellfish was previously correlated (as in June 1999) with blooms of the pennate diatom *Pseudo-nitzschia*, dominated most often by species of the «*pseudodelicatissima/cuspidata* complex» [1] or exceptionally by species of the «*seriata* complex». Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) analyses were performed and *P.*

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Fig. 2. Light micrograph of a chain of *Pseudo-nitzschia* cf. *multistriata*.

• Mexico

Bloom of *Chattonella subsalsa* in an impacted coastal lagoon in the Gulf of California

As in many countries, Mexico, with high population growth and increasing agriculture, mariculture, and tourism, has contributed to coastal eutrophication, providing conditions that favour development of harmful algae blooms (HABs). HABs are expected in areas with high nutrient input, and an increase in their occurrence in the last few years is often cited [1]. This has also been the case for Mexico [2]. An apparent increase of raphidophycean species (*Fibrocapsa*

japonica and *Chattonella* spp.) along Asian and European coasts has been reported [3]. Their presence is of concern because of their toxins. Massive poisoning of economically important fishes has been reported to be caused by the small *F. japonica*; toxicity of *Chattonella* spp. has also been related to fish kills [4].

The presence of *Chattonella* species in a limited number of Mexican coastal areas [5, 6] is noted in two previous reports of blooms in the Gulf of Cali-

fornia [7, 8], one of them associated with loss of marine resources [7]. However, the toxicity of these blooms has not been demonstrated in Mexican waters.

A bloom of *Chattonella subsalsa* was observed in Laguna Navachiste, Sinaloa on the eastern coast of the Gulf of California (Fig. 1). Laguna Navachiste is a shallow, semi-enclosed coastal lagoon characterized by harsh environmental conditions and severe

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pseudodelicatissima and *P. multiseriis* were identified respectively [2]. More recently, the toxic species *P. calliantha* (which belongs to the «*pseudodelicatissima/cuspidata* complex») was shown to be also present in French coastal waters (Billard, unpublished data).

At the end of October 2004, just before the opening of the harvesting period, and when DA was detected in king scallops from the Bay of Seine, field samples were examined to look for the diatoms suspected to be responsible for this contamination. A first investigation by light microscopy (LM) of bottom seawater did not detect the DA-producing benthic diatoms *Amphora coffaeiformis* or *Nitzschia navis-varingica*. On the other hand, cells and empty frustules of at least four species of *Pseudo-nitzschia* were present in low numbers. The most abundant featured narrow cells with sigmoid ends (Fig. 2) as in *P. multistriata* or wide symmetrical valves as in *P. fraudulentata*, and the least abundant showed wide asymmetrical (type A) or narrowly fusiform valves with coarse fibulae and interstriae (type B). The usually toxic

Fig. 1. Map with localization of the Bay of Seine.

«*pseudodelicatissima/cuspidata* complex» was absent.

During November 2004 a specific study was undertaken in several Bay of Seine sites and samples examined included: contents of scallop gastrointestinal tracts, sediment, bottom seawater and surface plankton (20 μm mesh size nets). Thorough LM analyses showed that only rare frustule fragments were present in scallops whereas rare sigmoid cells and a few empty frustules of the four species of *Pseudo-nitzschia*

non-toxic and other putative toxic *Pseudo-nitzschia* species were scarce in autumn of 2004, and in order to understand what had been responsible for the DA contamination, phytoplankton samples collected routinely in the Bay of Seine by the REPHY network during the previous summer were examined. A moderate *Pseudo-nitzschia* bloom was detected from mid-July to September, with a peak on September 14th, 2004 at 56,000 cells l^{-1} .

were recorded in the sediment samples; in bottom waters and surface nets, neither of the two morphotypes A and B was recorded. Three Bay sites sampled on November 29-30th for isolation of living cells and EM identification showed scarcity of *Pseudo-nitzschia*: two types only were recognized by LM, thin sigmoid cells and larger cells with symmetrical valves. The latter species, more abundant at the most coastal of the three sites, was isolated into unialgal culture and unambiguously identified by SEM as *P. fraudulentata* (Fig. 3).

Since *P. fraudulentata* is generally considered

Light microscopy observations showed that the *Pseudo-nitzschia* summer assemblages included only three morphotypes: *P. cf. fraudulentata*, but also types A and B. Either type A or B was dominant during the period of mid-July to September as shown by estimation of cell densities of individual types. Type A was not only characterized by asymmetrical valves but also by 7.5-8 μm wide cells, with important overlapping ends (25-28% of cell length) as in *P. australis* or *P. seriata*; type B with narrowly fusiform (4.5-6 μm wide) and coarsely silicified valves showed overlap of cell ends about 27-30% of length, as in *P. pungens* or *P. multiseriis*.

Species identification by transmission electron microscopy (TEM) was carried out on acid-cleaned frustules following the method of Lundholm & Moestrup [3]. Examination of a subsample of the September 14th 2004 surface water collection allowed us to formally

Fig. 3. *Pseudo-nitzschia fraudulentata*, SEM micrograph of valve showing central interspace, fibulae, interstriae and the typical poroid arrangement.

Fig. 4. TEM micrographs of valve views of *Pseudo-nitzschia* spp. with arrangement of poroids. a) *P. pungens*. b) *P. multiseries*. c-d) *P. australis*, with d) showing asymmetrical outline of the valve.

identify three species of *Pseudo-nitzschia*: *P. pungens*, *P. multiseries* and *P. australis* (Fig. 4). The first two, which are roughly similar in shape, are easily distinguished by their ornamentation, *P. pungens* with 2 rows of poroids between thick interstriae and *P. multiseries* with striae showing 3-4 rows of tightly packed poroids. *P. australis*, with large asymmetrical valves, features thin interstriae (18 interstriae in 10 µm and approximately the same number of fibulae) and 2 rows of poroids per valve

stria (4-5 pores in 1 µm). Following EM analyses, type A cells may therefore be assimilated to *P. australis*, while type B cells were either *P. pungens* or *P. multiseries*.

Individual chains of type A cells were isolated from a Lugol-fixed water sample collected in mid-August 2004 and processed for molecular analysis. The ITS1, 5.8S and ITS2 region and part of the 28S of the nuclear ribosomal DNA were sequenced following PCR amplifications. The resulting sequences

were compared with known sequences of *Pseudo-nitzschia* species from other geographic regions available in databases (Fig. 5) and shown to be identical (100 % identity) with two sequences of Scottish strains of *P. australis* [4] and with other strains of *P. australis* from U.S.A [5, 6], New Zealand [U92260, Haywood, A.J., *et al.*, direct submission] and Denmark [AF417651, Lundholm, N. *et al.*, direct submission]. Results of the molecular analyses therefore confirm once more that type A cells were of *P. australis* and, furthermore that this species was present in mid-August in the Bay of Seine.

Pseudo-nitzschia multiseries had never been recorded before in the Bay of Seine, while this is the first report for the occurrence of *P. australis* in France. Both these species, known to be highly toxic, co-occurred during the summer bloom of 2004 in the Bay. They are suspected to be the main source of DA in the king scallops, while *P. fraudulenta* and the *P. multistriata*-like cells could be potential secondary sources of DA.

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Fig. 5. Pair-wise distance calculations using MEGA 3.1 (Neighbor joining, Kimura 2-parameters), accession numbers of the aligned sequences, and one of the two similar obtained matrices.

	[1]	[2]	[3]	[4]	[5]	[6]	[7]	[8]
[1]								
[2]	0.000							
[3]	0.000	0.000						
[4]	0.000	0.000	0.000					
[5]	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000				
[6]	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000			
[7]	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000		
[8]	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	

[1] *P. australis* Bay of Seine-28S partial, [2] AY452530-*P. australis*-28S partial, [3] AY452529-*P. australis*-28S partial, [4] AF440768-*P. australis*-28S partial, [5] AF417651-*P. australis*-28S partial, [6] U92260-*P. australis*-28S partial, [7] U41393-*P. australis*-D1-D3, [8] U40850-*P. australis*-D1-D3.

[1] *P. australis* Bay of Seine-ITS1-2, [2] AY452528-*P. australis*-ITS1-2, [3] AY452527-*P. australis*-ITS1-2, [4] AY559850-*P. cf. australis*-18S part-28S part, [5] AY257842-*P. australis*-18S part-28S part

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Fig. 1. Navachiste-San Ignacio-Macapule lagoon system (Gulf of California) and location of *Chattonella subsalsa* patches (reddish-brown shaded area). Arrows indicate sewage drains.

Fig. 2. a-k *Chattonella subsalsa* collected at Laguna Navachiste. (a-j) live cells and (k) acid lugol fixed cells.

anthropogenic stress [9, 10]. Water temperature varies from 15.4 to 32.7 °C and salinity ranges from 30 to 45 psu [10]. Superimposed on the extreme environmental conditions are a series of unique environmental pressures. Sewage dumped into the lagoon is considerable. Major point-source pollutant inputs include sewage outfalls from Guasave City and outfalls associated with run-

off containing agricultural and aquacultural nutrients and waste. Discharges have been occurring for several decades [11, 10], and the long-term consequences of this situation are unknown.

This study includes quantification of a *C. subsalsa* bloom using 1% lugol fixed samples and the Utermöhl technique [12]. Identification of the species was achieved with unfixed samples

Table 1. Identified taxa in the *Chattonella subsalsa* bloom in Laguna Navachiste, Mexico.

Species	cells L ⁻¹
RAPHIDOPHYTES	
<i>Chattonella subsalsa</i>	952,059
DIATOMS	
<i>Actinocyclus</i> sp.	3,918
<i>Cerataulina pelagica</i>	7,836
<i>Chaetoceros curvisetus</i>	11,754
<i>C. diversus</i>	300
<i>C. lorenzianus</i> f. <i>forceps</i>	21,549
<i>C. compressus</i>	74,441
<i>Coscinodiscus granii</i>	3,918
<i>Cylindrotheca closterium</i>	15,672
<i>Guinardia striata</i>	15,672
<i>Navicula</i> sp.	3,918
<i>Navicula</i> sp. 2	27,426
<i>Nitzschia longissima</i>	121,456
<i>Nitzschia</i> sp.	11,754
<i>Odontella sinensis</i>	200
<i>Pseudo-nitzschia</i> sp.	11,754
<i>Pseudo-nitzschia</i> sp. 2	39,179
<i>Rhizosolenia setigera</i>	23,508
<i>Skeletonema costatum</i>	86,195
<i>Thalassionema frauenfeldii</i>	58,769
<i>T. nitzchioides</i>	39,179
<i>Thalassiosira</i> sp.	15,672
DINOFLAGELLATES	
<i>Gonyaulax verior</i>	3,918
<i>Gymnodinium</i> sp.	3,918
<i>Gyrodinium spirale</i>	3,918
<i>Prorocentrum micans</i>	7,836
<i>P. triestinum</i>	11,754
<i>Protoperidinium</i> sp.	7,836
CYANOPHYTES	
Cyanophyceae (tricomes)	19,590
NANOFLAGELLATES	
	223,322
Total	1,828,218

(Fig. 2a-j). As in previous studies [6, 8], cells fixed with lugol deformed and shrank, making it difficult to identify without observing unfixed cells (Fig. 2k). The reddish-brown bloom, dominated by *C. subsalsa* (Table 1), was observed on September 3rd 2005 with concentrations between 500,000 to 960,000 cells L⁻¹. Similar concentrations were reported in April 2003 at Kun Kaan on the Sonora coast [7] and in April-May 2005 in Bahía de La Paz near La Paz, B.C.S. [8]. Physical and chemical conditions during the bloom (Table 2) suggest favorable conditions for bloom development. Size of cultured cells (n = 34) varied from 31.5 to 46.5 µm long and 17 to 24.5 µm wide. Cells are rounded in the anterior portion; whereas the posterior portion is small and obtuse; and an uncolored posterior tail is present. From a deeper pore,

Table 2. Average physical and chemical variables during *Chattonella subsalsa* bloom in Laguna Navachiste, Mexico.

Temp (°C)	pH	Salinity (psu)	OD (mg/L)	Secchi (m)	Cl a (mg/m ³)	NO ₂	NO ₃	NH ₃	PO ₄
						(µM)			
33.1	7.9	38.5	6.8	0.5	8.7	0.28	0.64	4.4	0.46

two similar flagella emerge in opposite directions.

Blooms of *Chattonella* occurring during 2005 on both coasts of the Gulf of California indicate either that raphidophycean species have been overlooked for quite some time or that environmental conditions during recent years have become favorable for these algae. In future studies, cloned cultures will be used to determine toxicity and confirm identification of the species.

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• Italy

Blooms of *Mesodinium rubrum* in a coastal area of the Tyrrhenian Sea

Fig. 1 Gulf of Naples, Mediterranean Sea
* sampling station off Portici,
▲ the long term study site MC.

Blooms of the photosynthetic ciliate *Mesodinium rubrum* have been among the first sea-water discolorations ever documented. In 1827 the phenomenon was reported from Valdivia by the German naturalist Pöpping [1], and seven years later by Darwin from the Bay of Concepción and Valparaíso [2]. These events preceded by almost a century the description of the species [3], yet the information provided by Darwin was detailed enough for Hart [4] to attribute them to *M. rubrum* blooms [5]. Since then, red-water blooms caused by *M. rubrum* have been reported from coastal waters of almost all oceans. Outbreaks exceeding 1000 cells/mL are a common feature in summer along the Atlantic coasts of Portugal, Spain and Africa [6-

8] and in the UK [9, 10]. We report here information on blooms of *M. rubrum* in the coastal waters of the Southern Tyrrhenian Sea (Mediterranean Sea).

The most intense blooms were detected in the course of a national environmental monitoring program, along the coast of the Campania region, during which phytoplankton communities were investigated at several stations since June 2001. One monitored station is located 100 m off Portici (6 m depth), offshore a densely inhabited urban area (Fig. 1) which is characterised by nutrient enrichment due to urban sewage discharge and by continuous phytoplankton blooms (up to 16.6×10^4 cells/mL, 84% of diatoms) especially during periods of water column stratification (mainly May to September). On May 18, 2006, the surface waters off Portici showed a dark green-brownish colour and a considerable turbidity (Secchi disk depth 1 m). Utermöhl counts of a surface formaldehyde-fixed sample revealed a dense population of the mixotrophic ciliate *Mesodinium rubrum* (Fig. 2) (2.3×10^3 cells/mL). The accompanying phytoplankton population (4.2×10^4 cells/mL) was dominated by diatoms (84%), with *Skeletonema pseudocostatum* (39%) and small single-celled *Chaetoceros* spp. (36%) as the main taxa. *Mesodinium* concentrations on April 27 were 1.3×10^2 cells/mL while they

Fig. 2. Light micrograph of a formaldehyde-fixed cell of *Mesodinium rubrum*.

dropped below detection in the following sampling on May 31.

Despite the lower cell number, *Mesodinium rubrum* biomass was more than threefold that of the total phytoplankton ($3.5 \mu\text{gC}/\text{mL}$ and $1.05 \mu\text{gC}/\text{mL}$, respectively) due to the small size of the dominant taxa. The actual biomass value could have been underestimated, since *M. rubrum* is easily disrupted upon fixation with formaldehyde, which can cause about 60% loss as compared to Lugol's [11]. Correcting the cell counts for this theoretical loss the estimate would be 3.6×10^3 ind./mL, corresponding to $5.6 \mu\text{gC}/\text{mL}$. Despite the considerable disproportion in biomass, the abundance of the rest of the population was probably high enough to mask the

Fig. 3: Seasonal cycle of *Mesodinium rubrum* at the monitoring station off Portici (2001-2006).

red colour that is commonly reported for *M. rubrum* blooms [12].

As for the environmental conditions during the bloom, surface water temperature (21.16°C) was higher and salinity (36.40 psu) lower than the mean values of the month for the station (20 °C and 37.14 psu, respectively). Nutrients were extremely high (total nitrogen 46.5 µmol/L; total phosphorous 1.6 µmol/L and silicate 12.6 µmol/L) as often occurs in the area (mean values 28.6 µmol/L, 1.2 µmol/L, 5.9 µmol/L, respectively). Rapid heating of the surface water layer was recorded during the month of May, from 18.62°C on April 27 to 22.88°C on May 31 after which the surface temperature dropped to 20.44°C on June 13. The high temperature and low salinity values, coupled with high nutrient concentrations, are indicative of a very high retention rate which could have favoured the accumulation of the bloom. *Mesodinium rubrum* blooms are in fact not a rare event in the area. Comparably high concentrations (1.5×10^3 cells/mL) were also registered in June 2001 (Fig. 3) and the highest annual abundances of the species are usually recorded from May to August, which is also the period of maximum concentrations of the rest of the phytoplankton. It is conceivable that during these periods particular hydrographic/meteorological situations may lead to favourable conditions for more conspicuous outbreaks from time to time.

The blooms of *M. rubrum* seem to be confined to the very inner part of the Gulf of Naples, since much lower concentrations (below 100 cells/mL) were observed during a long term study

at the site MC, 2 nm off Naples [13], which also correspond to the values reported for other sites of the Mediterranean Sea [14]. The only bloom of *M. rubrum* (3.9 µgC /mL) reported for this basin was observed in a highly eutrophic lagoon of the Po Delta area (Adriatic Sea) [15]. The peak abundance and biomass values of *M. rubrum* at the Portici station are comparable to those recorded during outbreaks at other sites; however even higher abundances [8, 16] have been recorded off Portugal and Mexico and up to 11 µgC/mL in the Kuril Islands (N. Pacific, Russia) [17]. Blooms of *M. rubrum* have frequently been reported associated with high numbers of dinoflagellates [6] or, as also observed in the Gulf of Naples, with diatoms [18]). Low salinity and high temperatures at surface in high nutrient areas are generally associated with the occurrence of *M. rubrum* blooms, which typically last only a few days [19].

Our observations in the Gulf of Naples show that *M. rubrum* can reach high concentrations in eutrophic Mediterranean coastal waters especially during the warmer season, when the recreational use of the sea is enhanced. Only a few other reports of discolorations caused by other species exist for the Tyrrhenian coasts [20-23], probably because these events may not be easily ascribed to phytoplankton blooms. However their impact on the aesthetic quality of the sea could seriously impinge on tourism and recreational activities that are among the major resources in many coastal Mediterranean areas.

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• Mexico

Fish mortality associated with *Chattonella marina* and *C. cf. ovata* (Raphidophyceae) blooms in Sinaloa (Mexico)

Fig.1. Foam associated to blooms of *Chattonella* spp. Daily News Debate (May 9, 2006).

Fig.2. Fish mortality location and study area.

From April to May, 2006, three red tide events occurred in Sinaloa, México. The red tide forming species were *Chattonella marina* and *C. cf. ovata*, the toxic dinoflagellate *Gymnodinium catenatum* was present during this period in low densities in Bahía de Mazatlán. The total number of red tide days was 33 days. The first bloom occurred on March 16-22, the species of highest abundance was *C. marina*. The second bloom was on April 10-14 and the third bloom occurred April 26 to May 12; both blooms were formed by *C. marina* and *C. cf. ovata*. The last bloom (from May 1-12, 2006) is detailed in this report. On the Sinaloa coast, strong discolorations in the sea were witnessed in the study period. The water was a yellow-brown colour; with abundant foam forming stripes parallel

to the coast (Fig.1). On May 3-4, fish mortality occurred on some beaches of Sinaloa, the first off San Lorenzo River (Cosalá), the second in El Walamo (Mazatlán) and Las Cabras (Escuinapa) (Fig. 2). These mortalities could be associated with red tide events caused by *Chattonella* spp. This is an ichthyotoxic species, a producer of reactive oxygen species (ROS), and of haemolytic and neurotoxic substances. These microalgae affect fish gills and cause death. Initial inquiries suggested the fish mortality was associated with

chemicals used cleaning a sugar refinery in the first case, and oxygen depletion (caused by discharged shrimp fishery waste) in the second case. Nevertheless, these fish mortalities occurred during this red tide period and could contribute synergistically to fish mortality. There are no studies to prove this, but the great volume of dead fish in Las Cabras could not have been discharged from the two shrimp vessels. Besides, the seasonal prohibition for shrimp capture begins March 24. The dead organisms included benthic fish, mollusks and crustaceans, but most of the fish were a pelagic species ("palometas", *Trachinotus paitensis*), used for human and livestock consumption (Figs. 3. A, B).

Fig. 3. A, B. Fish mortality on Las Cabras beach. Daily News Noroeste (May 4, 2006).

Table 1. Count of *Chattonella* spp. (in vivo) in Bahía de Mazatlán.

Day-May	Cells ml ⁻¹
3	750
5	95
7	228
10	74
12	35
15	0

Fig. 4. Rhabdophyceans in vivo (blue) and fixed (rouse): (A-B) *Chattonella marina*, (C-D) *C. cf. ovata*, (E-F) *Chattonella marina* round form and (G-H) Temporary cyst form (scale = 50 µm).

Table 2. Phytoplankton composition and abundance of *Chattonella* spp. bloom in Bahía de Mazatlán (May 6, 2006).

Species	Cells ml ⁻¹	Abundance %	Toxin associated
<i>Chattonella marina</i> and <i>C. cf. ovata</i>	332	46.56	Ichthyotoxicity ROS, hemolysis
Peridiniaceae: <i>Peridinium</i> spp. and <i>Protoperidinium</i> spp.	172	24.12	
<i>Gymnodinium catenatum</i>	148	20.76	PSP
<i>Pseudo-nitzschia</i> sp.	15	2.10	ASP
<i>Ceratium falcatum</i>	10	1.40	
<i>Prorocentrum gracile</i>	9	1.26	
<i>Gyrodinium</i> sp.	5	0.70	
<i>Thalassiosira</i> sp.	4	0.56	
<i>Scrippsiella trochoidea</i>	4	0.56	
<i>Gymnodinium</i> sp.	4	0.56	
<i>Ceratium balechii</i>	3	0.42	
<i>Dyctiocha fibula</i>	3	0.42	
<i>Ceratium furca</i> var. <i>hircus</i>	3	0.42	
<i>Prorocentrum micans</i>	1	0.14	
Total	713	100.00	

The yellow-brown discoloration of the sea water produced abundant brown foam along the Sinaloa coast. Sampling for this study were carried out in Bahía de Mazatlán. The physical-chemical conditions in the discoloration zone were: surface temperature 21.2-22.7°C, salinity 34.5-34.7 psu, and dissolved oxygen 5.3 mg l⁻¹. Surface samples were collected daily in Bahía de Mazatlán. The identification, photography and quantification were carried out *in vivo* in light microscope with 40x objective. Cell abundance declined between May 1 and May 15 (Table 1). On May 5 surface samples were fixed, settled for 12 h and quantified with an inverted microscope [1]. The method indicated a phytoplankton abundance of 713,000 cells·l⁻¹. *Chattonella marina* and *C. ovata* were distinguished by their size and number (Fig. 4). The abundance of both species was 332 000 cells·l⁻¹ and they constituted 46.5% of the phytoplankton composition (Table 2). This may be an underestimate since fixation destroys many cells. These cells were 30-70 µm long and 20-30 µm wide (Fig. 4), deformed, and some round like temporary cysts (Fig. 4. G, F), similar to those observed in Kun Kaak Bay [2]. Recently, some authors have reported the presence of Raphidophyceae in Mexican Pacific, blooms without fish mortality effects [4, 5]. This study represents the second case of a massive fish mortality associated with *Chattonella* spp. [2]. We not were able to identify species affected, but a conservative estimate is 12,000 to 15,000 fish. or about 48-60 tons of fish, distributed on 3 km of beach from Las Cabras to El Palmito del Verde (taking in consideration 4-5 fishes, 3-5 kg per 1 m²).

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GEOHAB

Global Ecology and Oceanography of Harmful Algal Blooms

GEOHAB Core Research Project – HABs in Upwelling Systems: Call for Participants

The GEOHAB report on *HABs in Upwelling Systems* (GEOHAB, 2005 <http://ioc.unesco.org/hab/Upwelling%20IP-2006%20Final.pdf>) specified that GEOHAB would form a subcommittee for the Upwelling Core Research Project. The Subcommittee began its work with a meeting in Villefranche, France on 18-21 January 2006. All four major eastern boundary current upwelling systems were represented: the Benguela Current (Grant Pitcher and Trevor Probyn), Iberian Current (Teresa Moita and Francisco Figueiras), California Current (Raphael Kudela and Vera Trainer), and Humboldt Current (Sonia Sánchez).

The Subcommittee identified six key questions related to HABs in upwelling systems for which some research is already ongoing and for which a core set of scientists for GEOHAB-related research could be identified. Full descriptions of the projects can be found at <http://ioc.unesco.org/hab/Upwelling%20IP-2006%20Final.pdf>, including the motivation for the projects, likely participating regions, a project coordinator and participants, project objectives, project approach and work plan, example projects, and expected project output. The intention is that this list will expand as more scientists worldwide link their research to these projects. We invite interested participants to contact the Project Coordinator for more details, or to indicate interest in these projects.

An immediate goal of the HABs in Upwelling Systems subcommittee is to summarize research to date in each of the project areas with the help of

colleagues familiar with those areas of research. We envision a research publication detailing new work in each area of focus (review papers) specifically highlighting areas of need that will help to strengthen interest in collaborative studies. Please contact project coordinators to express your interest in contributing your expertise for research papers. We would also like to list a complete set of publications, including “gray” literature, in each research area for each upwelling region. This Core Research group will hold an evening discussion session on Wednesday, September 6, 2006 at the 12th International Conference on Harmful Algae in Copenhagen, Denmark to which all interested researchers are invited.

1. Project: Effects of nutrients on HAB population dynamics in upwelling systems

Project Coordinator: Trevor Probyn, Marine & Coastal Management, Cape Town, South Africa

Contact: tprobyn@deat.gov.za

Project objectives

- Quantify the importance of upwelled nutrients to HABs as the f-ratio (N-based).
- Provide physiological understanding of HAB species' nutrition (N, P, Si) and biological supply mechanisms (regeneration).
- Determine the role of trace metals in HAB dynamics.
- Identify how nutrient availability and speciation may affect cellular toxicity (N, P, Si, trace metals).
- Provide input to HAB biogeochemical models.

Motivation

A defining attribute of upwelling systems is the periodic supply of nutrients from deeper waters that provides appreciable scope for phytoplankton growth and concomitant effects on higher trophic levels. Given the compelling evidence for a global increase in HABs, and their established negative impacts in coastal upwelling environments, it is important to understand how this potential production is channeled into HABs as opposed to, or as a successional stage of, the more benign/beneficial blooms that generally characterize these regions. In this regard, there appears to be a dearth of information in coastal upwelling ecosystems relating specifically to the nutritional aspects of HABs compared to the more typical non-HAB, diatom-dominated assemblages.

2. Project: Climate and HABs in upwelling systems

Project Coordinator: V. Trainer (NOAA Fisheries, USA)

Contact: Vera.L.Trainer@noaa.gov

Project Objectives

To investigate potential correlations between “long-term” HAB monitoring data (shellfish toxicity, toxigenic species, continuous plankton recordings) and local environmental data (e.g., nutrients, wind, temperature) as well as regional and global climate indicators (ENSO, PDO, NAO).

Motivation

Changes in upwelling intensity provide one of the substantiated lines of evidence for warming climatic trends, although the specific regional responses are still being established.

Several research groups have documented a correlation between HAB events (frequency and magnitude) and changing climate indicators. For example, HAB events are believed to be occurring more frequently during El Niño/Southern Oscillation (ENSO) events in the Humboldt Current system when low abundance of diatoms coincides with increasing numbers of new species (primarily dinoflagellates, including some toxigenic species) resulting in serious problems to the anchovy fishery, while ENSO events have also been correlated with toxic HAB events in Mexico. There is a need to compare interannual variability of HABs among upwelling systems as well as at different latitudes within a system. The study of regions in different hemispheres will allow comparisons to be made on the effects of the seasonal timing of arrival of climatic signals on HABs.

Influences of climate require well-documented time series of a sufficient duration to characterize the underlying mechanisms. Research needed to establish linkages between HABs and climate change includes data-mining efforts for short-term time series (examination of time series and satellite data), as well as projects involved in micro-paleontology (dating and characterizing sediment cores) for longer time series, and finally development of hindcast and forecasting models to help apply the knowledge gained to our understanding of HAB dynamics.

However, comprehensive, complete, long-term HAB datasets and corresponding environmental data are rarely available. Many HAB data are collected by managers only when necessary for the protection of public health, resulting in incomplete time series or inconsistent datasets. Effective time-series analysis requires very large data sets; an appropriate data policy conducive to data sharing (i.e., individual investigators will be willing to share data knowing that it will only be used for meta-analysis) will need to be established. Furthermore, care will need to be taken to differentiate climatic effects from other long-term changes such as urbanization and land-use practices, fresh-water diversion, etc.

3. Project: Genetic comparisons of HABs in upwelling systems

Project Coordinator: R. Kudela, University of California Santa Cruz (USA)

Contact: kudela@cats.ucsc.edu

Project Objectives

- Molecular characterization (e.g. sequence analysis for application of RNA/DNA molecular probes) for harmful algal species in each region
- Based on (1), determine whether HAB producing organisms are genetically distinct for the comparable regions
- Utilize differences in cell toxin quota of a given species in separate upwelling regions to allow characterization of genes and biochemical pathways important for toxin synthesis

Motivation

This project will address the role of genetic predisposition versus environmental conditions in toxin production in different upwelling systems within a given genus or species. It is well known that toxigenic HAB species exhibit variability in toxin production, both at the species and genus level, within a given upwelling system. Multiple environmental factors have been shown to influence HAB toxicity and ecology and it is possible that the entire range of observed spatial and cell-specific variability in toxin production is a response to subtle environmental cues. However, variability in genotypes is a common feature of phytoplankton. These genotypic differences are responsible for markedly different phenotypic expression in response to environmental cues within the same putative species. Therefore, the variability in toxin production is likely caused by a combination of genotype and environmental conditions. A genetic comparison of HAB organisms among regions is useful for differentiating between genetics and environment. Although there are several genetic comparisons that could be identified, here we focus on four potential targets that are found in all regions: *Pseudo-nitzschia* spp., *Protoceratium reticulatum*, *Lingulodinium polyedrum*, and *Alexandrium catenella*.

4. Project: Coastal morphology and its influence on HABs in upwelling systems

Project Coordinator: G. Pitcher (Marine & Coastal Management, Cape Town, S. Africa)

Contact: gpitcher@deat.gov.za

Project objectives

To establish the importance of coastline morphology and bathymetry in:

- creating local upper mixed layer conditions favourable for the selection and development of HABs and;
- determining bay circulation patterns favouring bloom development through retention.

Motivation

Alongshore variability of coastal upwelling is mainly controlled by the interaction of the wind-forced shelf flow with coastline and bottom topography, resulting in the amplification and or reduction of upwelling-downwelling processes (Figueiras et al. in press). Consequent spatial variability in upper mixed layer characteristics and shelf flow related to coastline discontinuities, such as pronounced capes, coastal embayments or Rias (in northwestern Iberia), often favours HAB development by enhancing vertical stratification and by forming regions of retention. Comparative research within these regions will serve to assist in identifying the underlying physical processes responsible for the higher incidence of HABs within these regions.

5. Project: Seeding strategies within upwelling systems

Project Coordinator: A. Amorim (U. Lisbon, Portugal)

Contact: ajamorim@fc.ul.pt

Project Objectives

- To identify seed populations of particular HAB species in relation to oceanographic features important to their development.
- To describe sedimentary processes determining the location and accumulation of seedbeds (e.g. dinoflagellate cyst beds).
- To describe the seeding and overwintering strategies of particular HAB species.

6. Project: The role of across-shelf and along-shore currents in the transport of HABs in upwelling systems

Project coordinator: F.G. Figueiras (IIM-CSIC, Spain)

Contact: paco@iim.csic.es

Project objectives

- To determine the relative importance of alongshore and across-shelf transport within the 4 regional upwelling systems in the initiation, accumulation, and transport of harmful algae to coastal environments.

Motivation

Upwelling systems are essentially heterogeneous with mesoscale structures such as eddies, fronts, filaments and river plumes interacting with alongshore and across-shelf currents. These currents are among the most important physical features of upwelling systems and frequently interact to influence HABs in upwelling regions (e.g. Fraga et al. 1988, Pitcher et al. 1998, Trainer et al. 2002). Alongshore currents are able to transport blooms from their sites of initiation while on-shore transport, associated with downwelling, often favours bloom accumulation in coastal waters where they impact fisheries and tourism. Offshore transport resulting from upwelling promotes their dispersion from coastal systems. Understanding the relative contribution of alongshore and across-shelf flow to the transport of harmful algae to and from the coast will be important in the development of accurate physical-biological models. Comparison among systems will aid to reinforce observations and refine models.

Contributed by GEOHAB Core Research Program: HABs in Upwelling Systems Steering Committee members: Grant Pitcher, Chair; Francisco Figueiras, Raphael Kudela, Trevor Probyn, Teresa Moita, Sonia Sánchez, Vera Trainer, Ed Urban, and Henrik Enevoldsen

- To determine the role of environmental parameters in species-specific seeding strategies (e.g., in establishing cyst dormancy, germination, growth, and the periodicity of blooms).
- To determine whether strategies of seeding between upwelling regions are similar.

Motivation

The identification of seed or overwintering populations and the establishment of seeding strategies are important in understanding the development of HABs in upwelling systems, which are recurrent but not always predictable. To better understand and model HABs, species-specific life-history transitions, which may determine the initiation or termination of a bloom, must be considered as an important source of variance. In upwelling systems, advective processes are important in determining species-specific overwintering and seeding strategies. For example, the encystment and excystment of dinoflagellates is often used to explain seasonal patterns, however very few studies have been conducted in the field. In areas where these studies have been performed results indicate that closely related species differ markedly in their adaptive strategies despite their similarity in life-history transitions and habitat (e.g. Montresor et al. 1998). Dale and Amorim (2000) suggested three different seedbed strategies for HAB

dinoflagellates: (1) those species without resting cysts, (2) those species heavily dependent on seedbeds, and (3) those species that produce large numbers of cysts but are seemingly independent of seedbeds. These strategies should be investigated for different dinoflagellate species within and between upwelling systems. Diatom populations such as *Pseudo-nitzschia* are often associated with thin layers both in the water column and near-bottom (e.g. Rines et al. 2002). Cells under these low light conditions are found to be viable, indicating that *Pseudo-nitzschia* may be present as “shade flora” in stratified water masses, which may function as seed-beds under favorable conditions. Other physical settings, including mesoscale eddies and frontal systems, have also been found to favour the accumulation of *Pseudo-nitzschia* populations. The existence of a *Pseudo-nitzschia* resting stage has been suggested, but no clear seeding strategy has been established.

Understanding and comparing species-specific seeding strategies in different upwelling systems will be useful in the development of models aimed at forecasting blooms and their impacts in coastal regions. A collaborative approach using standardized methods will benefit attempts to establish the sites of seedbeds and to determine the seeding strategies for HAB species in upwelling systems.

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Future events

HABTech '07 Workshop

March 15-17, 2007. Nelson, New Zealand.

HABTech '07 is a workshop dedicated to new technologies for the detection of harmful algal blooms and toxins. The third HABTech workshop is being hosted by Cawthron Institute in Nelson, New Zealand, and is being held immediately prior to the International Conference on Molluscan Shellfish Safety to enable delegates to attend both events. For more information please visit: www.cawthron.org.nz/habtech07/habtech-07-workshop.html

ICMSS 07

March 18th- 23rd, 2007. Blenheim, New Zealand.

New Zealand is hosting the 6th International Conference Molluscan Shellfish Safety in Blenheim. The conference is held every two years and brings together scientific, industry and regulatory people from all over the world. The conference agenda will allow the sharing of scientific research, management systems, debate on international trade issues and networking between stakeholders.

More details can be found on www.nzfsa.govt.nz/icmss07.

HARMFUL ALGAE NEWS

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